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Learning Style and Achievement: A Correlational Study

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Learning style group common ways in which people learn. Learning style is a term used to portray individual differences in the way that people prefer to learn. Learning styles are typical patterns individuals use to process information or approach learning situations. Learning style preferences are thought to occur naturally. According to learning style theory, when an individual's learning preferences are met, the individual learn more easily and effectively. It is important to acknowledge learner diversity and to customize and individualize learning. When learners understand how they prefer to learn, they can seek preferred learning settings and learn to cope with setting that do not align to their learning preferences. Teachers, administrators and program planners can use learning style information while planning teaching strategies and learning activities, evaluating learning and developing program and curricula. Education about learning style will help teachers recognize their preferred learning and teaching styles and provide alternative ideas and strategies to help teachers incorporate multiple teaching strategies to facilitate the needs of individuals with different learning styles. Learners who understand their own learning style can also recognize and seek learning situations that match their preferences and learn to develop skills and strategies for success in condition that do not match their learning styles. In another words, an individual has one or more than one learning styles. When the individual has more than one learning style the levels of using it can change. Learning styles has cognitive, affective and psychological aspects. Cognitive components are about the internal control of the system of running the knowledge and these can be changed through education. Affective and psychological component affect the preferences of the individual and suggest answer to both education and teaching strategies. Learning style give opportunities to recognize the individuals and the differences between them. For this reason, a teaching style is required to devise learning approaches that take cognitive affective and psychological factors into account. An advantage of the identification of the own learning style by the student is that it will help the student to become an effective problem solver. The more successful the individual is at solving the problems s/he faces, the more control s/he will take over his/her own life. It is important that individual receive education in areas suitable for their learning styles. A person educated in an area having no relationship to his/her learning style may lack confidence and s/he may be less successful; s/he may as a result become frustrated. Knowledge of learning style also provides information to the student as to why s/he has learnt in a different way than others. It helps to control the process of learning. It is vital because one of the most important signals in learning is to learn to be autonomous, that is for the individual to take responsibility for his/her own learning. When the student take responsibility for their learning as they are at the centre of the process and everything is under their control. They search answers to the problems and benefit from their

unique performances and preferences in their learning styles. They know what they want to learn and “how”. This awareness will change their perspectives on learning new things. It is commonly believed that learning styles are not really concerned with “what” learners learn, but rather “how” they prefer to learn and it is also an important factor for student’s academic achievement and attitudes. Knowledge of one’s learning styles can be used to increase self-awareness about their strength and weaknesses as learners. But Merrill (2000) argued that most students are unaware of their learning styles. Matching student’s learning style preferences with complementary instruction improves academic achievement and student’s attitude towards learning (Coffield, Hall and Ecclestone; 2004). According to Sathl (2002) it has been an utter failure to find that assessing children’s learning style and matching them to instructional methods has any effects on their learning. Dunn, et al. (1995) suggested that matching student’s learning style preferences with educational interventions compatible with those preferences is beneficial to their academic achievement. The purpose of this study was to investigate the learning styles of student-teachers enrolled in B.Ed course. It is a well-known fact that teachers are very effective agents of student’s learning. Teachers need to develop their knowledge in both subject matter and pedagogy to meet student’s demand in the classroom. For this reason, teacher training programs should provide variety of learning environments to allow student-teachers for gaining necessary skills.

It is found that teachers’ learning style, teaching style and personality affect students’ achievement and attitudes towards any subject. According to Sarasin (1999), teaching cannot be successful without a knowledge of learning styles and a commitment to matching them with teaching styles and strategies.” There have been a number of researches conducted to show the relationship between learning style and academic achievement, and which show that matching teaching styles to learning styles can significantly enhance academic achievement of students at any level (Griggs and Dunn, 1984; Smith Renzulli, 1984). Most researchers in the field of learning styles agree that enabling learners to reflect on how they learn best helps to develop their metacognition. Fostering metacognition is perhaps the most important advantage that can be claimed for applying learning style theory to teaching and learning which in turn develop effective learners who can handle changes in a learning context and excel in examinations. Learning style consideration in learning is therefore an approach that is directed at meta learning, similar to setting goals, choosing appropriate strategies and monitoring progress which are more effective ways of improving learning outcomes and achievements than those which simply aim to engage learners at the level of presenting information or understanding and use (Hattie, Biggs and Purdie, 1996).

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY-

The objectives of the present study were as follows-

1. To find out the relationship between learning style and marks achieved in internal assessment among science stream B.Ed. students.

2. To find out the relationship between learning style and marks achieved in external assessment among science stream B.Ed. students.
3. To find out the relationship between learning style and marks achieved in internal assessment among arts stream B.Ed. students.
4. To find out the relationship between learning style and marks achieved in external assessment among arts stream B.Ed. students.

* All the objectives were achieved with reference to six types of learning styles i.e. Enactive Reproducing, Figural Reproducing, Verbal Reproducing, Enactive constructive, Figural constructive and Verbal Constructive.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES-

Following research hypotheses have been formulated-

1. There is relationship between learning style and marks achieved in internal assessment among science stream B.Ed. students.
2. There is relationship between learning style and marks achieved in external assessment among science stream B.Ed. students.
3. There is relationship between learning style and marks achieved in internal assessment among arts stream B.Ed. students
4. There is relationship between learning style and marks achieved in external assessment among arts stream B.Ed. Students.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY-

Researcher has adopted survey method of descriptive research for present study. The sample consisted of 72 Female B.Ed. Students of S.S.Khanna Girls Degree College Prayagraj. Out of which 36 B.Ed. students were of science stream and 36 were of arts stream. For measuring learning style, Learning Style Inventory by K.S.Misra has been used, for internal achievement sum of marks obtained in B.Ed. semester I and II in internal assessment has been used as an index of achievement. For external achievement sum of marks obtained in B.Ed. semester I and II in external assessment has been used as an index of achievement. Pearson's Correlation Coefficient has been used for the analysis of the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION-

Table-1

Values of coefficient of correlation between learning style and marks achieved in internal assessment among science stream B.Ed. students.

S.No.	Learning style	Correlation Coefficient value
1.	Enactive Reproducing(ER)	0.067
2.	Figural Reproducing (FR)	-0.013
3.	Verbal Reproducing (VR)	0.272
4.	Enactive Constructive (EC)	0.205
5.	Figural Constructive (FC)	0.222
6.	Verbal Constructive (VC)	0.211

It has been hypothesized that “there is no significant relationship between learning style and marks achieved in internal assessment among science stream B.Ed. students of science background.” Table-1 shows that the values of coefficient of correlation between all the six learning styles namely-enactive reproducing, figural reproducing, verbal reproducing, enactive constructive, figural constructive and verbal constructive and marks achieved in internal assessment are 0.067, -0.013, 0.272, 0.205, 0.222 & 0.211 which are not significant at .05 level. So the hypotheses can be accepted with regard to all the six learning styles and it can be said that there exists no relationship between learning styles and marks achieved in internal assessment by science stream B.Ed. students.

Table-2

Values of coefficient of correlations between learning style and marks achieved in external assessment among science stream B.Ed. students.

S.No.	Learning style	Correlation Coefficient value
1.	Enactive Reproducing(ER)	0.003
2.	Figural Reproducing (FR)	-0.050
3.	Verbal Reproducing (VR)	0.294
4.	Enactive Constructive (EC)	0.034
5.	Figural Constructive (FC)	0.039
6.	Verbal Constructive (VC)	0.216

It has been hypothesized that “there is no significant relationship between learning style and marks achieved in external assessment among science stream B.Ed. students.” Table-2 shows that the values of coefficient of correlation between all the six learning styles namely- enactive reproducing, figural reproducing, verbal reproducing, enactive constructive, figural constructive and verbal constructive and marks achieved in external assessment are 0.003, -0.050, 0.294, 0.034, 0.039, 0.216 respectively which are not significant at .05 level. So the null hypotheses can be accepted and it can be inferred that there exists no relationship between learning styles and marks achieved in external assessment.

Table-3

Values of coefficient of correlation between learning style and marks achieved in internal assessment among Arts stream B.Ed. students.

S.No.	Learning style	Correlation Coefficient value
1.	Enactive Reproducing(ER)	0.120
2.	Figural Reproducing (FR)	0.314
3.	Verbal Reproducing (VR)	0.425*
4.	Enactive Constructive (EC)	0.136
5.	Figural Constructive (FC)	0.119
6.	Verbal Constructive (VC)	0.067

*Significant at .05 level

It has been hypothesized that “there is no significant relationship between learning style and marks achieved in internal assessment among Arts stream B.Ed. students.” Table-3 shows that the value of coefficient of correlation between verbal reproducing learning style and marks achieved in internal assessment is 0.425 which is significant at .05 level. So, the null hypotheses can be rejected. It means that verbal reproducing learning style is positively related to marks achieved by Arts stream B.Ed. students in internal assessment. The values of coefficient of correlation between other learning styles namely-enactive reproducing, figural reproducing, verbal reproducing, enactive constructive, figural constructive and verbal constructive and marks achieved in internal assessment are 0.120, 0.314, 0.136, 0.119 and 0.067 respectively which are not significant at 0.05 level. So the corresponding hypotheses can be accepted. It can be said that there exists no relationship between enactive reproducing, figural reproducing, verbal reproducing, enactive constructive, figural constructive and verbal constructive and marks achieved by Arts stream B.Ed. students in internal assessment.

Table-4

Values of coefficient correlation between learning style and marks achieved in external assessment among Arts stream B.Ed. students.

S.No.	Learning style	Correlation Coefficient value
1.	Enactive Reproducing(ER)	0.075
2.	Figural Reproducing (FR)	0.210
3.	Verbal Reproducing (VR)	0.321*
4.	Enactive Constructive (EC)	0.183
5.	Figural Constructive (FC)	0.129
6.	Verbal Constructive (VC)	0.119

*Significant at .05 level.

It has been hypothesized that “there is no significant relationship between learning style and marks achieved in external assessment among Arts stream B.Ed. students.” Table-4 shows that the value of coefficient of correlation between verbal reproducing learning style and marks achieved in external assessment is 0.321 which is significant at .05 level. So, the null hypotheses can be rejected. It means that verbal reproducing learning style is positively related to marks achieved by Arts stream B.Ed. Students in external assessment. The values of coefficient of correlation between other learning styles- enactive reproducing, figural reproducing, enactive constructive, figural constructive and verbal constructive and marks achieved in external assessment are 0.075, 0.210, 0.183, 0.129 and 0.119 respectively which are not significant at .05 level. So, the null hypotheses can be accepted and it can be said that there exists no relationship between enactive reproducing, figural reproducing, enactive constructive, figural constructive and verbal constructive and marks achieved by Arts stream B.Ed. students in external assessment.

On the basis of the findings of the study it can be concluded that verbal reproducing learning style is positively related to academic achievement among Arts stream B.Ed. Students while enactive reproducing, figural reproducing, enactive constructive, figural constructive and verbal constructive are not related to academic achievement among both arts and science stream B.Ed. students. It means that Arts stream B.Ed. students benefit more from verbal reproducing learning style as this style develops the ability among these learners to be actively engage in listening and absorb information effectively. They have the quality of paying close attention to verbal instructions, lectures, discussions and conversations. Verbal reproducers have a talent for reproducing information in their own words. They can accurately recall and recite key details, concepts or explanations. They have the ability to express themselves verbally, both in spoken and written form. They can express their thoughts clearly, engage in meaningful

discussions and present information effectively. Verbal reproducers often possess a strong vocabulary, grammar and language comprehension. They can understand complex tests, utilize language nuances and understand construct coherent sentences. Verbal learners thrive in group environments where discussion and debate occur. They can actively participate, contribute ideas and benefit from peer interaction. Their strong verbal skills enable them to convey their knowledge and ideas confidently which in turn positively shows enhancement in their academic achievement. They tend to participate actively in classroom discussions and ask insightful questions which deepens their understanding and facilitate higher levels of achievement. The present findings draws support from the findings of Thakkar (2014), uzuntiryaki, John, Shahzadi & Khan (2016). They also found no relationship between learning style and academic achievement. However, Orhun & Orhun(2007), Malathi and Malini (2010), Sharma (2011) found relationship between learning style and academic achievement. Vaishnav (2013) reported relationship between kinesthetic learning style and academic achievement. Thus it can be concluded that there is ignorance among students and teachers concerning learning styles. That's why students do not use these styles in learning process. Perhaps there exists a mismatch between learning style of B.Ed. Students and instructional methods used by teacher educators. This has resulted in existence of no relationship between various learning styles and internal as well as external assessment of B.Ed. Students of Science and Arts background. The findings of the present study implies that verbal reproducing learning style must be encouraged among students in order to increase their achievement.

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